

Organic Derivatives of Silicon. Part V. Reactions of Silicon Tetra-acetate with Glycols: Synthesis of Glycol Derivatives of Silicon

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The reactions of silicon tetra-acetate with various glycols in different molar ratios have been studied. In most cases diglycollates are formed, even when reactants are taken in 1:1 molar ratio, leaving half the tetra-acetate unchanged. With hexylene glycol different compounds are formed in different molar ratios. The mechanism of the reaction, the properties, and other characteristics of the various silicon derivatives have been studied.

The preparation and properties of glycol derivatives of aluminium¹, boron², titanium³, germanium⁴, and zirconium⁵ have been studied in detail. A few reactions between silicon tetrachloride and glycols, reported in the literature, have been found to yield a mixture of products⁶. Moreover, the product obtained on refluxing silicon tetrachloride with an excess of ethylene glycol was found to contain chloride⁷ and this might be either due to slowness of the reaction or more probably due to the side reactions of hydrogen chloride initially formed. The ease with which silicon tetra-acetate has been found to interchange its acetoxy groups with alcohols⁸ and a number of other organic reagents⁹ led us to investigate the reactions of silicon tetra-acetate with glycols.

The reactions of silicon tetra-acetate with various glycols were attempted in different molar ratios. In almost all the cases, even when the reactants (silicon tetra-acetate and glycol) were taken in 1:1 molar ratio, the diglycollates were formed and half of the tetra-acetate remained unchanged. It was only in the case of hexylene glycol that different compounds were obtained in different molar ratios. The silicon derivatives of ethylene glycol and propane-1,2-diol are non-volatile solids, insoluble in benzene. The butane-diol derivatives have also been found to be undistillable but are soluble in benzene. The dipinacolate has been found to sublime, whereas the hexylene glycol derivatives distil under reduced

1. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 635.
2. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1032.
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4. Mehrotra and Chandra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2904.
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7. Jacovig, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1956, 288, 324.
8. Kali-Chemie, D.R.P. 909, 153/1954; *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, 48, 11893.
9. Pant, B. C., Ph. D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1963.

pressure and are soluble in benzene. The various reactions may be represented as follows:

- (i) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{R}'''=\text{H}$.
 (ii) $\text{R}=\text{Me}; \text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{R}'''=\text{H}$.

- (iii) $\text{R}=\text{R}''=\text{Me}; \text{R}'=\text{R}'''=\text{H}$.
 (iv) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{R}'''=\text{Me}$.

- (i) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{H}; \text{R}'''=\text{Me}$.

- (ii) $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{R}''=\text{Me}; \text{R}'''=\text{H}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

Benzene (B.D.H.) was refluxed over metallic sodium, distilled, and finally dried azeotropically with ethanol. The various glycols were purified by distillation. Silicon tetra-acetate was prepared by the reaction of silicon tetrachloride with an excess of *t*-butyl acetate¹⁰.

Silicon was estimated by decomposing the compound with a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc., A.R.) and HNO_3 (conc., A.R.) in a platinum crucible and then final ignition to silica. The pinacol was estimated by dichromate oxidation methods¹¹.

10. Mehrotra and Pant, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, No. 5, 321.

11. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 3919.

Reactions between Silicon Tetra-acetate and Ethylene Glycol

(i) *In 1:1 molar ratio.*—To silicon tetra-acetate (5.28 g.) were added ethylene glycol (1.24 g.) and benzene (25 ml). The contents were thoroughly shaken when an appreciable amount of heat was generated. The shaking was continued for about 10 min. when a glassy mass was formed. It was dried at 40°/0.05mm for 3 hr. when a white amorphous powder was obtained. It was washed 5-6 times with benzene and the solution was decanted. The insoluble product was dried again (1.29 g.). [Found: Si, 18.92. Si(O₂C₂H₄)₂ requires Si, 18.95%].

The benzene solution on evaporation under reduced pressure provided white crystals (2.57 g.). [Found: Si, 10.59; OAc, 89.39. Si(OAc)₂ requires Si, 10.63; OAc, 89.37%].

TABLE I

Reactants.	Nature of the product and %yield.	Found.	Reqd.	Distillation or sublimation.
Si(OAc) ₄ + ethylene glycol	Si(O ₂ C ₂ H ₄) ₂ ; amorphous powder; 86%	Si : 18.92% **G : 80.00	18.95% 81.05	
Si(OAc) ₄ + propane-1,2-diol	Si(O ₂ C ₃ H ₆) ₂ ; white amorphous powder; 90%	Si : 15.84 G : 84.20	15.94 84.06	
Si(OAc) ₄ + hexylene glycol	(H ₃ COCO) ₂ Si(O ₂ C ₆ H ₁₂) ₂ ; a colorless liquid; 97%	Si : 10.62 G : 44.20	10.70 45.01	68-92°/0.4-0.6mm
Si(OAc) ₄ + pinacol	Si(O ₂ C ₆ H ₁₂) ₂ ; shining crystals; 86%	Si : 10.71 OAc : 89.40	10.78 89.20	110-16°/1.5 mm

*Calculated on the basis of silicon.

**G stands for glycol.

(ii). *In 1:2 molar ratio.*—To silicon tetra-acetate (2.64 g.) were added ethylene glycol (1.24 g.) and benzene (20ml). An exothermic reaction occurred when the contents were

TABLE II

Reactants.	Nature of the product and yield.	Found.	Reqd.	Distillation or sublimation.
Si(OAc) ₄ + ethylene glycol	Si(O ₂ C ₂ H ₄) ₂ ; white amorphous powder; 99%	Si : 18.92 G : 81.00	18.95 81.05	
Si(OAc) ₄ + propane-1,2-diol	Si(O ₂ C ₃ H ₆) ₂ ; white amorphous powder; 99%	Si : 15.92 G : 84.00	15.94 84.06	
Si(OAc) ₄ + butane-1,2,diol	Si(O ₂ C ₄ H ₈) ₂ ; viscous liquid; 96%	Si : 13.50	13.75	
Si(OAc) ₄ + butane-2,3-diol	Si(O ₂ C ₄ H ₈) ₂ ; white crystals; 95%	Si : 12.93	13.75	
Si(OAc) ₄ + hexylene glycol	Si(O ₂ C ₆ H ₁₂) ₂ ; white semisolid; 99%	Si : 10.87	10.78	66-67°/0.3mm
Si(OAc) ₄ + pinacol	Si(O ₂ C ₆ H ₁₂) ₂ ; white crystalline solid; 97%	Si : 10.51 G : 89.80	10.78 89.20	110-15°/1.5 mm

thoroughly shaken and a glassy mass was obtained. The contents were shaken further for 40 minutes and dried at $40^{\circ}/0.01$ mm for 3 hr. A white amorphous powder (1.46 g.), insoluble in benzene, was obtained. [Found: Si, 18.92; $C_2H_4O_2$, 80.90. $Si(O_2C_2H_4)_2$ requires Si, 18.95; OAc, 81.05%].

The reactions are summarised in Tables I and II.

One of the authors (B.C.P.) is thankful to the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

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Received March 3, 1964.